

Human Influence on Marine Biodiversity: Vulnerabilities and Challenges

Cintia Cardoso¹

Captain & Marine Science Specialist, Brazil¹

Master's Marine Science and Technology¹

Student of Maritime, Port and Customs Law ¹

Abstract

In recent years, growing concern about the health of the oceans has gained prominence in the environmental debate. Marine environments, which encompass a vast diversity of species and ecosystems, are facing a series of threats exacerbated by human actions. The unbridled exploitation of natural resources, pollution, ocean acidification and climate change are putting at risk not only marine biodiversity, but also life on the planet as a whole. In this context, the relationship between the carbon cycle and ocean temperature emerges as a crucial factor to be considered in efforts to protect these vulnerable ecosystems.

Keywords Oceans, Biodiversity, Acidification, Climate Change, Marine Pollution.

1. INTRODUCTION

The oceans play a vital role in regulating the Earth's climate, acting as a major carbon sink. The ocean's ability to absorb carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere is critical to mitigating climate change (Doney et al., 2009).

According to the IPCC (2021), the oceans have absorbed approximately 30% of the CO₂ emitted since the Industrial Revolution, resulting, among other things, in the acidification of ocean waters.

This process, which decreases the pH of the water, directly affects marine life, especially calcareous organisms such as corals, molluscs and some species of plankton, which depend on calcium carbonate to form their skeletons and shells (Doney et al., 2009).

According to CARDOSO, C.C. (2024), understanding this interconnection between the carbon cycle and marine biodiversity is essential to develop effective conservation strategies.

Acidification is just one of several threats facing the oceans, and investigating the multiple pressures on these ecosystems is crucial to ensuring their health and resilience (Doney et al., 2009).

2. BEYOND ACIDIFICATION: OTHER THREATS TO MARINE LIFE

Global warming, driven by increased greenhouse gas emissions, is raising the temperature of ocean waters CPA Cintia, C. (2024). This phenomenon is alarming, especially for corals, which are extremely sensitive to temperature changes (CPA CARDOSO C., 2024)

The phenomenon of coral bleaching, caused by thermal stress, has become increasingly common, resulting in the death of extensive areas of coral reefs, considered the most biodiverse ecosystems on the planet (Doney et al., 2009).

The loss of these habitats compromises not only marine fauna and flora, but also the human communities that depend on them for food, tourism and coastal protection (Doney et al., 2009).

In addition to acidification and rising temperatures, marine pollution, especially from plastics, has had devastating impacts on marine life. Every year, millions of tons of plastic are dumped into the oceans, affecting marine fauna that mistake these materials for food or become entangled in them (Rochman et al., 2013).

This pollution not only threatens the survival of countless species, but also contaminates the food chain, eventually impacting humans who consume seafood (Rochman et al., 2013).

According to estimates, around 700 marine species are directly affected by plastic waste, contributing to a loss of biodiversity that cannot be ignored (UNEP, 2021).

Another crucial factor in the scenario of marine vulnerability is overfishing. The increased demand for seafood and the overexploitation of species have pushed many fish stocks to the brink of collapse (Doney et al., 2009).

Illegal, unregulated and unreported fishing is of particular concern, as it exceeds sustainable limits and harms the recovery of fish populations. The decline in key species affects not only marine biodiversity, but also the health of ecosystems, which depend on a balance between their various components (CPA CARDOSO C., 2024).

In this scenario, it is imperative that we adopt a multidisciplinary and comprehensive approach to address the challenges facing marine environments. Implementing sustainable fishing practices, creating marine protected areas, and reducing carbon emissions are crucial steps (Friedlingstein et al., 2019).

Environmental education and raising awareness about the importance of the oceans and marine biodiversity are also essential to mobilize society around the cause (Rochman et al., 2013).

Furthermore, strengthening public policies that encourage marine preservation and developing sustainable economic alternatives for coastal communities can help mitigate pressures on these ecosystems (CPA Cintia, C., 2024).

According to Rochman et al., (2013), science plays a fundamental role in monitoring environmental changes and assessing the impacts of human actions on marine life, contributing to the formulation of evidence-based conservation strategies.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In short, the vulnerability of marine environments and their biodiversity is a reflection of human actions that, cumulatively, have caused deep and lasting damage (CPA CARDOSO C., 2024).

The relationship between the carbon cycle and ocean temperature exemplifies how climate change directly impacts marine ecosystems, affecting biodiversity and, consequently, human life (Doney et al., 2009).

It is essential to act collectively, adopting a responsible stance regarding our impact on the oceans (CPA Cintia, C., 2024).

Only through awareness, education and the implementation of effective solutions can we guarantee the health and diversity of marine environments for future generations (Rochman et al., 2013).

The time to act is now, because the preservation of our oceans is an issue that transcends borders and concerns us all (CPA CARDOSO C., 2024).

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